

TECHNOLOGY OF ASSIMILATION OF MATERIALS FOR THE TEACHING UNIT "STATISTICS AND PROBABILITY" IN XI CLASSES OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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Abstract

In the article, it is included in the content of Mathematics subject in XI classes of general education schools "Statistics and Probability" the content of the skills intended to become the subjects of the students in the process of teaching the materials for the educational unit was presented. Content elements that carry the "enabling function" in the formation of these skills "Statistics and Probability" attention is paid to their presence in the educational unit and to the technology of turning them into action in the students' cognition (adequate to the "movement-possibility-new quality" paradigm). "Statistics and Probability" "System-structure" of the transformed elements in the teaching unit based on the dialectical approach "Statistical indicators: dispersion and standard deviation", "Forms of data distribution. Normal distribution", "Box - handle diagram", "Random Events and Probability" it is considered appropriate to make it into a system on topics. It should be noted that the system of tasks (question, problem, study) that serves as a means of organizing and managing the educational process for mastering the content elements presented by the students should contain verbs that are required to be performed in the topics. Examples of tasks of that kind are included in the content of the work.

Keywords: probability; statistical indicators; random events; dispersion; standard deviation; information distribution forms; normal distribution; chart; box-handle diagram.

The actuality of the subject. There are no recommendations that are useful to be adopted for guidance in the teacher's activity in the currently used textbook complex [7-8] and various educational literature about the teaching units, basic standards, sub-standards, and defined topics in the subject of mathematics. These are very useful in terms of teaching the process of teaching mathematics according to the curriculum model. It is not denied that continuous improvement of the teaching process in the subject is logical, most didactic problems are eternal. Of course, as the experience of using the curriculum is formed, the methodical system (technology) of the teaching process adequate to it should also be improved. Based on this logic, "Technology of mastering materials for the teaching unit "Statistics and Probability" in XI grades of general education schools" We claim the relevance of the research of the topic.

Interpretation of generalizations based on information obtained on the basis of research.

In order to clarify the logic of the presented scientific interpretation, let us note that in the summarization of the materials obtained on the research topic, in addition to referring to the forms and methods of scientific cognition, "training and teaching activity", "learning and mastering", "content and content line", "main standard with the expected result", "main standard and sub-standards", "system-whole-part-element relations" were focused [2].

Scientific sources indicate that "training" and "educational activity" are one of the main concepts of pedagogy. Although training is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not cover all aspects of it. Training, in the broadest sense of the word, involves the acquisition of new knowledge, skills and habits. However, learning and learning activities are essentially different events. Appropriation is an integral part not only of the learning process, but of every field of activity [1;150].

The analysis of the materials obtained from scientific sources leads us to the conclusion that training is a way of implementing education, and the fact that spiritual learning, memorizing what has been learned, and acquiring the experience of creative activity based on it depends on the way of learning (the dialectic of the content and form of cognitive action). Formation of the educational space in didactics according to the associations of industrial revolutions and formation of the model of its implementation is an eternal problem [3].

Based on the idea of L.Bertalanfi to get to the essence of many pedagogical concepts, to give an honest scientific interpretation, in our opinion, it is a successful approach [9; 8]. By the way, let's emphasize that the "system-structural approach" is a developed branch of dialectics, which has gained an independent "status" since the 30s of the 20th century [5-6].

The technology of education implementation (methodology in the traditional approach) has its own system [10]. The expected result in the mentioned tech-

nological system is determined by the state of movement of the selected content. A technological system is available for each educational unit. It is not accidental that the selection of the teaching unit is brought to the center of attention in the design of the mentioned system [2-3].

The main and sub-content standards of the "Probability and statistics" section, expressed (called) in the form of the same name, contained in the "Statistics and probability" content line in the XI grades of the general education school, are: 5.1. Collects statistical data, systematizes, analyzes and presents the result; 5.1.1. Calculates the variance and mean square measure of the measurement; 5.2. Understands and applies basic concepts of probability theory; 5.2.1. It applies the normal distribution law to the calculation of the probability of the event [8;5].

"Statistics and Probability" in the process of teaching the topics covered in the educational unit, students are expected to become subjects of the following skills:

It presents the data according to statistical indicators that characterize the distribution, such as numerical mean, median, mode, central tendency, and the largest difference; It calculates the trend, variance, standard deviation according to the database given in various forms; Demonstrates an understanding of the relationship between the value of the standard deviation and the distribution of data values by showing examples; Constructs a normal distribution curve for the sample (population) and presents it according to the situation; A graph presents information according to the numerical mean and standard deviation in a normal distribution; Determines and presents data according to the conditions required in the normal distribution with calculations; Solves problems related to probability according to the normal distribution curve; Divides the data into quartiles; Presents data with a threaded box diagram; Demonstrates understanding of concepts such as random event, random event space, trial, event; Applies probabilities to the calculation of events that match and do not match the set; Apply the rule of multiplication of probabilities to the occurrence of independent events; Apply the conditional probability formula to problem solving;

Mastering the materials of this educational unit, students' active mathematical vocabulary includes the following concepts - population, selection, numerical mean, mode, median, tendency, mean square deviation, dispersion, box-handle diagram, event, random event, experiment, elementary event, elementary events space, allows to enrich it with independent events, dependent events, conditional probability and considerations related to them [8; 260].

It is recommended to take advantage of virtual tools (important links for teaching the course [11-17]) and various worksheets as additional resources in teaching the materials of the "Statistics and Probability" educational unit.

It is enough to devote 2 hours to the teaching of the subject "Statistical indicators: dispersion and standard deviation". At the beginning of the teaching of this topic, in order to master the concepts of "Dispersion" and "standard deviation", the necessary parts of the

content of the teaching materials about "numerical mean", "mode", "median" used in analyzing statistical data are reproduced. For this purpose, it is recommended to benefit from the application of reproductive studies and heuristic methods. Students remember that they used "numerical mean", "mode", and "median" indicators to analyze statistical data. They know that: the numerical mean is found using the values of all the data, and deviations can lead to wrong conclusions about the population as they affect its value. Median is the middle value of data arranged in ascending order. The median divides the data into two halves—lower and upper halves. It is a more reliable statistic when outliers exist and is useful for analyzing a limited amount of data. The mode defines characteristic information for the population, which allows us to think about the numerical mean, and is more convenient for the analysis of categorical data (gender, color, etc.). Data can have more than one mode or no mode [7; 261].

Summarizing the restorative activities of the students, the teacher informs them that in order to draw more correct conclusions based on statistical data, indicators such as tendency, dispersion, and standard deviation are used to characterize them. The bias is the difference between the data value and the numerical mean $x_{bias} = x - \bar{x}$, where x the given numerical value of the data, $\bar{x}$ is the numerical average. Dispersion is the ratio of the sum of the squares of the trends to the number of data values and is denoted by σ^2 and $\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2}{n}$, where n is the number of data values. The standard deviation is called the square root of the variance and is usually denoted by the letter: σ – sigma: $\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma^2}$. The standard deviation is an important statistic that characterizes the distribution of data. The standard deviation shows the distribution of data values according to the numerical mean, and the farther apart the data values are, the greater the standard deviation. The closer the data values are to each other, the smaller the standard deviation. In other words, if the data is concentrated around the numerical mean, the standard deviation is small.

The teacher should use these tasks in order to regulate the environment for deeper assimilation of this information given to the students. This is an approach tested by practitioners, its effectiveness is not in doubt. The following can be included among such examples [7; 261-263].

Example. The weekly salary of 10 randomly selected employees in the company is as follows: 120, 160, 90, 175, 110, 80, 220, 150, 300, 95 manats. Calculate the mean, variance, and standard deviation for this data and explain the situation.

Solution:

1. Let's make a table according to the salaries.
2. Let's calculate the numerical mean: $\bar{x} = 1400: 10 = 140$.
3. By subtracting the numerical average from each salary amount, its deviation from the numerical average is found.

For example, $120 - 140 = -20$, this person's salary is 20 manat less than the average weekly salary. Let's add a column to the table showing the trend ($x_i -$

$\bar{x}$) for each salary. The trends of the individual data sum to zero. This is always the case and does not provide new information. Therefore, the sum of the squares of the trends is used.

4. Let's calculate each $(x_i - \bar{x})^2$ - and record it in a new column in the table and find the sum: $\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2$

$$\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = 43150.$$

To calculate the variance, divide the sum we find by the number of data n ($n = 10$):

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n} = \frac{43150}{10} = 4315.$$

Numerical average $\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x_i}{n} = 140$

Salary	Tendency: $(x_1 - \bar{x})$	Square: $(x_1 - \bar{x})^2$
120	-20	400
160	20	400
90	-50	2500
175	35	1225
110	-30	900
80	-60	3600
220	80	6400
150	10	100
300	160	25600
95	-45	2025
Total: $\sum x_i = 1400$	Total: $\sum (x_i - \bar{x}) = 0$	Total: $\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2$

5. To find the standard deviation of wages, take the square root of the variance: $\sigma = \sqrt{\sigma^2} = \sqrt{4315} \approx 65,69$

It is explained to the students that the change in wages can be estimated according to the standard deviation. For example, a person earning 300 manat earns more than 2 standard deviations (2×65) more than the average weekly salary (140 manat). A person who receives a weekly salary of 90 manats is paid approximately one standard deviation (65) less than the weekly salary.

Continuing the teaching process, at this point it would be useful to bring to the students' attention an example of finding the standard deviation of grouped data.

Example. The number of students who missed daily lessons in a class for 50 days is given. Calculate the standard deviation.

Solution:

1. First, let's group the data according to the number of students who missed classes daily and record it in the frequency table. For example, the number of days that no one misses class is 10, the number of days that 1 student misses class is 19, etc.

The number of students who missed daily lessons in a class during 50 days

1	3	1	1	1	1
5	0	1	2	2	1
0	1	1	0	0	0
3	6	2	3	0	1
1	3	0	3	1	1
1	1	6	0	1	3
4	1	1	6	6	1
2	2	2	0	3	0
2	4				

2. Let's find the numerical mean according to the information we received from the table.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x \cdot f}{n} = \frac{91}{50} \approx 1,8.$$

3. The trend of each data: a) is found from the numerical average value: $(x_i - \bar{x})$; b) squared: $(x_i - \bar{x})^2$; c) the obtained result is multiplied by the number n , added and divided to get the square root.

x_i	f_i	$x_i f_i$
0	10	0
1	19	19
2	7	14
3	7	21
4	2	8
5	1	5
6	4	24
	$\Sigma = 50$	$\Sigma = 91$
$x_i - \bar{x}$	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2$	$(x_i - \bar{x})^2 f_i$
-1.8	3.24	32,40
-0.8	0.64	12,16
0.2	0.04	0,28
1,2	1.44	10,08
2.2	4.84	9,68
3.2	10,24	10,2470,56
4.2	17.64	

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 f_i}{n}} = \sqrt{\frac{145,4}{50}} \approx 1,71$$

As it can be seen, the number of children who do not come to class daily is 1.71 with a standard deviation and an average of 1.8 [6; 172-175].

It is recommended to apply a system of tasks made into a special system for students to master the theoretical materials related to the topic "Statistics: dispersion and standard deviation", to include them in the existing practice base and to develop the relevant skills in students. We consider it expedient to include the following task examples in the mentioned system.

1. Complete the tasks according to the given information.

100; 200; 300; 400; 500; 600; 700; 800; 900; 1000.

a) Find the numerical mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation (σ);

b) Multiply the value of each data by 10. Find the mean ($\bar{x}$) and standard deviation (σ) for the new data.

c) Divide the price of each item by 10. Find $\bar{x}$ and σ .

d) Discuss your thoughts on the results. Explain whether the numerical mean is the correct indicator for assessing the condition of the value of the standard deviation.

2. The results of 8 girls and 8 boys randomly selected from among the SAT (Scholastic Aptitude Test) test takers are as follows.

Boys' SAT scores: 1059; 1328; 1175; 1123; 923; 1017; 1214; 1042.

Girls' SAT scores: 1226; 965; 841; 1053; 1056; 1393; 1312; 1222.

a) Find the largest variance, variance, and standard deviation for each group of data.

b) Explain the result according to the real situation.

3. Find the largest variance, mean, variance, and standard deviation that fit the data.

a) 11; 10; 11; 7; 8; 11; 6; 4; 6; 7

b) 13; 15; 13; 17; 18; 13; 15; 14; 13; 20; 20; 18; 23; 20 and so on.

"Forms of information distribution. Normal distribution" it is considered acceptable to allocate 2 lesson hours to the teaching of the subject. It is recommended to provide the students with information in the following content.

The students are told that according to the shape of the frequency distribution, the appropriate graphic shapes (histogram or frequency polygon) can be symmetrical or asymmetrical:

1. Normal distribution; 2. Right-skewed distribution (positive distribution); 3. Left-skewed distribution (negative distribution).

We can say about the normal distribution: The normal distribution curve is symmetrical with respect to the numerical mean: In the normal distribution, the numerical mean, median, and mode are equal; The graph of the normal distribution is constructed according to the numerical mean $\bar{x}$ and standard deviation σ . "The normal distribution" basically reflects the data around three standard deviations [8; 266].)

Students should know that the graph of a normal distribution shifts to the right or to the left depending on the value of the numerical mean. The graph is compressed or stretched by changing the standard deviation at the same value of the numerical mean.

In the process of teaching the subject, it is important to involve students in the activities of systemized learning tasks, and the normal distribution form should be mastered by them.

First, in order to visualize the form of normal distribution, students' involvement in the following example leads to effective results.

Example. In a normal distribution corresponding to any population X , the numerical mean is 40 and the standard deviation is 5. What percentage of grades included in this collection: a) is less than 45? b) is between 30 and 45 [8; 267].

After the implementation of the example, it is useful to continue the process of teaching the subject by engaging the students in several learning tasks as follows.

1. It is known that the numerical mean is 72 (points) and the standard deviation is 6 (points) in the normal distribution corresponding to the test.

1) Write the following information: a) those located around 1 standard deviation from the numerical mean;

b) those located around 2 standard deviations from the numerical mean; c) those located around 3 standard deviations from the numerical mean.

2) Draw a curve corresponding to a normal distribution. Show each interval as a percentage.

2. Plot the normal distribution curves in the same coordinate system. Explain the similarities and differences between these graphs.

a) numerical mean 50 percent, standard deviation 10

numerical mean 50 percent, standard deviation 20

b) numerical mean 50 percent, standard deviation 5

numerical mean 40 percent, standard deviation 5.

3. The test results were presented with a normal distribution. According to the results, the numerical average is 70, the standard deviation is 4.5. 360 people participated in the exam.

1) If a random person is chosen, the probability that he/she: a) is among those who scored in the interval of 65-80; b) the possibility of being among those who scored not less than 75 points; c) Find the probability that he is among those who scored less than 62. 2) Calculate the range in which 90% of test takers score, etc.

"Box - Handle Diagram" it is enough to allocate 2 lesson hours to the teaching of the subject. How to construct a box-handle diagram can be explained to the students on the following example.

Example. Scores of 15 employees of the company during the safety standards exam was like: 13; 9; 18; 15; 14; 21; 7; 10; 11; 20; 5; 18; 37; 16; 17. Present this information with a box-and-handle diagram.

1. By arranging the data in ascending order, the median is determined and denoted by Q_2 ($Q_2 = 15$);

2. Data to the left of the median form the lower half, and data to the right form the upper half. That is, the median divides the data into two halves.

3. The medians of the halves, called quartiles (here, divides the data into 4 parts. $Q_1 = 10$, $Q_3 = 18$)

4. Interquartile variation is determined: $Q_3 - Q_1 = 18 - 10 = 8$.

5. The smallest and largest values of the information given on the number axis, the values of the quartiles and the median - 5 important points are noted. A rectangle is drawn whose length is equal to the interquartile range. This rectangle is divided into two parts by the median. Then, by combining the corresponding quartiles with the largest and smallest values, the handles of the box are drawn (the steps performed in the process should be visually accompanied, otherwise the steps taken may be difficult for students to understand) [4; 452-453].

Thus, a box-handle diagram is constructed according to the given data. According to the diagram, the data is presented as follows: in about half of the 15 people, 50% of the participants scored between 10 and 18. 25% scored less than 10, 25% scored more than 10. The difference in the length of the left and right handle depends on the difference in the values of the information in the corresponding part.

Note that the activity on the sample should be generalized.

When building a box-handle diagram, 5 pieces of information are determined according to the given population: median- Q_2 , median-quartile Q_1 of the lower part where the data smaller than the median is collected, median-quartile of the upper part where the data is greater than the median is collected, the smallest value and the largest value.

Steps to construct a box-and-handle diagram:

1. A horizontal straight line is drawn;
2. Divisions with a certain scale are set according to the data change range;
3. The 5 specified data - Q_1, Q_2, Q_3 , the smallest value, the largest value - are recorded on a straight line;
4. A box is drawn up Q_1 to Q_3 ;
5. Handles are drawn from the smallest price Q_1 to the largest price Q_3 .

Students are engaged in cognitive activity on another example, as follows lays the foundation for a more sophisticated mastery of the steps of constructing a box-and-handle diagram.

Example. The ages of the members of the Paralympic women's volleyball team are as follows: 24; 30; 30; 22; 25; 22; 18; 25; 28; 30; 25; 27. Present the data with a box-handle diagram.

"Box-handle diagram", it is recommended to master the building steps by the students, to include them in the existing experience base and to apply a system of tasks made into a special system for the development of the relevant skills in the students.

"Random Events and Probability" it is enough to devote 4 hours of study to the subject. On the topic "Random events and probability". students are given information in the following content.

It is explained to them that the branch of mathematics that studies the regularity of random events is called probability theory. This theory studies not individual events, but the results of many experiments, that is, regularities of massive random events. Probability is a mathematical-numerical characteristic of the possibility of a certain event occurring under certain conditions.

A probable event is certain to occur as a result of experiment, experiment, or observation, and an impossible event never occurs. Events are conventionally interpreted as complex (separable) and elementary (non-separable) events. Each inseparable result of an experiment, experiment or observation is called an elementary event. The set of all elementary events is called the space of elementary events or test space. All possible outcomes of a particular experiment or observation $E_1, E_2, \dots, E_n$ the space of elementary events if it has elementary events $U = \{E_1, \dots, E_n\}$ can to any subset of the space of elementary events *is called an "event"*.

This time the empty set ($\emptyset$) impossible event, U and it will probably be an event. Since each event is a subset of the space of elementary events, actions assigned to sets are assigned to events in the same way [4; 455-458]:

- An event whose outcomes are all included in at least one of events A or B is called a combination of events A and B and is denoted by $A \cup B$.

- An event whose outcomes include both event A and event B is called the intersection of events A and B and is denoted as $A \cap B$.

- Events that do not have common outcomes are called incompatible events.

- The set of all outcomes not included in event A is called the counter event of event A and is denoted as $\bar{A}$.

- If every consequence of event A is also a consequence of event B, event A is said to cause event B, or event B is a consequence of event A, and this fact is written as $A \subset B$.

- An event whose results are not included in event B, but only included in event A, is called the difference between event A and event B. Denoted as $A \setminus B$.

In the course of teaching the subject in the series of trials of the event **frequency** is introduced to the concept. They understand that if we denote the total number of trials by n and the number of trials in which event

A occurs during n trials by $n(A)$, the $\frac{n(A)}{n}$ ratio is

called the frequency of event A in this series of trials. The probability of a random event can be approximated by the frequency of a series of multiple trials:

$P(A) \approx \frac{n(A)}{n}$; The probability $P(A)$ does not depend

on whether the test is passed or not, this number characterizes the random event A. The probability of a random event is the number to which the values of the observed frequency converge during numerous trials. Such a definition of probability is called a statistical definition. It should be clear to the students that the elementary events of the test occurring under the same conditions and under the same conditions are called equal opportunity events if one has no advantage over the other. The ratio of the number of favorable outcomes for event A to the number of all equally likely events is called the probability of event A and is denoted by $P(A)$: $P(A) = \frac{n(A)}{n}$ (1). This definition is

noted by $P(A)$: $P(A) = \frac{n(A)}{n}$ (1). This definition is

called the classical definition of the probability of an event. $0 \leq n(A) \leq n$ since it follows from formula (1) that $0 \leq P(A) \leq 1$; $E_1, E_2, \dots, E_n$ if all events are favorable to event A , i.e. if $n(A)=n$, then $P(A) = \frac{n}{n} = 1$

Probably the probability of the event is equal to 1. If neither outcome is favorable to event A , that is, if A is an impossible event, then $n(A)=0$ and $P(A)=0$. The probability of an impossible event is zero. Here it is useful to bring the following property to the attention of students.

Property. Equally possible $E_1, \dots, E_n$ elementary events have the same probability and the sum of these probabilities is equal to 1.

Indeed, suppose event $A E_1, \dots, E_n$ coincides with one of the events, e.g. $A = E_1$ is Then $E_i \cap E_j = \emptyset$ since $i \neq j$ when $A \neq E_i$ happens. So, $n(A) = n(E_1) = 1$. According to formula (1)

$$P(A) = P(E_1) = \frac{1}{n}.$$

A similar rule shows that $P(E_2) = \frac{1}{n}, \dots, P(E_n) = \frac{1}{n}$; From here it follows that $P(E_1) + P(E_2) + \dots + P(E_n) = 1$

The given theoretical information should be clarified by special studies. For this purpose, the following examples can be used:

1. There are 10 white and 15 black balls in a box. Find the probability that a ball drawn at random is black.

2. There are 10 white and 15 black balls in a box. Taking a ball out of the box and suppose that the ball is black. Let's put it aside and take a ball out of the box. Let's find the probability that this ball is also black.

3. There are 10 white and 15 black balls in a box. Two balls are drawn from the box at a time. Find the probability that both balls are black.

4. There are 7 white, 5 red, and 8 yellow balls in the box. Let us denote the event of a drawn ball being white by A , the event that it is red by Q , and the event that it is yellow by S , and find the probability of each of these events.

5. A coin is tossed twice. In both cases, you have to find the probability that the face with the coat of arms falls.

6. While inspecting a batch of 200 identical parts, the technical control department discovered 6 non-standard parts. Let's find the probability that a detail drawn at random is not standard.

7. The probability of hitting a target with pistol fire is 0.75. If 200 shots are fired, how many bullets can be expected to hit the target?

Students should know that they calculate the probability of a complex event by dividing it into events with known probabilities. As is known, $U = \{E_1, \dots, E_n\}$ each of the space of elementary

events E_k element is called its probability and is not negative $P(E_k)$ numerically opposed that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n P(E_k) = P(E_1) + \dots + P(E_n) = 1 \text{ condition}$$

is paid. Then, U - or probability space is called. Probability space $(E_1, \dots, E_n; P_1, \dots, P_n)$ or (U, P) is marked as It follows that for every $k 0 \leq P(E_k)$; $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$

Since each event A is a certain subset of the space of elementary events, it has a separation over elementary events, that is, a certain E_{k_p} for elementary phenomena $A = \bigcup_p E_{k_p}$ happens. The probability $P(A)$ of the event A is the sum of the probabilities of the elementary events in its division by elementary events. $P(A) = P\left(\bigcup_p E_{k_p}\right) = \sum_p P(E_{k_p})$

It is useful to familiarize students with the following theorems, which play an important role in probability theory.

Theorem 1. a) any anesthetic $A \subset U$ and $B \subset U$ for events $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B)$; b) $P(\emptyset) = 0$; c) $A \subset U, B \subset U$ and $A \subset B$ for any events A and B satisfying their relations $P(A) \leq P(B)$; c) any $A \subset U$ the same is paid for the event and its opposite event; d) any $\bar{A} P(A) = 1 - P(A)$ $A \subset U$ and $B \subset U$ for events $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$ attitude is correct.

The property of the theorem in clause a) can be summarized as follows: pairwise disjoint $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n$ the probability of the combination of events is equal to the sum of their probabilities, that is, $i \neq j$ when $A_i \cap A_j = \emptyset$ while

$$P\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n A_i\right) = \sum_{i=1}^n P(A_i).$$

This property is called the property of summation of probabilities.

• B is a positive probability event and A is any event $P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)}$

the quantity is called the conditional probability of the event A under the condition of occurrence of the event B . It follows that $P(A \cap B) = P(A) \cdot P(B \setminus A)$

This property is called the property of multiplication of probabilities.

Theorem 2. U is a space of elementary events with equal possibilities. Certain $B \subset U$ any within the condition of occurrence of the event $A \subset U$ conditional probability of an event

$$P(A|B) = \frac{n(A \cap B)}{n(B)}$$

is found by the formula

Theorem 3. U the space of elementary phenomena is not matched in pairs $B_1, \dots, B_n$ separated by events, namely:

$$U = B_1 \cup \dots \cup B_n \quad \text{and } i \neq j \text{ for } B_i \cap B_j = \emptyset. \text{ Then, for any event } A$$

$$P(A) = \sum_{i=1}^n P(A|B_i)P(B_i) = P(A|B_1) \cdot P(B_1) + \dots + P(A|B_n) \cdot P(B_n)$$

formula is correct. This formula is called the complete probability formula.

- $0 < P(B) < 1$ when

$$P(A) = P(A|B) \cdot P(B) + P(A|\bar{B}) \cdot P(\bar{B}).$$

In order to achieve the expected result in the process of teaching the subject, students should be familiar with the concept of independent events. They are informed by the following information.

Suppose that A and B are two different nonempty events of the space of elementary events. If the occurrence of event A does not depend on the occurrence of event B,

$P(A|B) = P(A)$ we can write (assuming that $P(B) > 0$). Then the conditional probability

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)}$$

from the formula we get

that $P(A \cap B) = P(B) \cdot P(A)$

• Events A and B $P(A \cap B) = P(B) \cdot P(A)$ when they satisfy the relation they are called independent events.

It should be noted here that this definition $P(B) = 0$ in the case, that is $P(A|B)$ is true even if the conditional probability is not specified.

• If events A and B are independent, known $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$ the formula $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A) \cdot P(B)$ can be written as

Any $k = 1, \dots, n$ and $i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq n$ for $P(A_{i_1} \cap \dots \cap A_{i_k}) = P(A_{i_1}) \cdot \dots \cdot P(A_{i_k})$

when paid $A_1, \dots, A_n$ a system of events is called a system that is independent of the totality.

$A_1, \dots, A_n$ in the case of a system that is independent of the whole, in the special case, $P(A_1 \cap \dots \cap A_n) = P(A_1) \cdot \dots \cdot P(A_n)$ the probability multiplication formula is obtained.

As is known, according to the classical definition of probability, to find the probability of event A in a given problem, it is enough to divide the number of elements of A (the number of "favorable cases") by the total number of elements appearing in the considered problem (the number of "possible cases"). Finding the number of favorable and feasible cases when looking at phenomena with finite element results is, in many cases, possible through the application of combination theory. In this direction, a task system should be applied

for the purpose of forming students' skills. The following can be used as an example [6; 195-196].

1. There are 9 rows in the auditorium of the cinema, and 9 seats in each row. The audience takes a random seat. Is it more likely that the sum of the numbers of the row and the place in the row is even or odd? (the sum is even more likely)

2. (Selection by return). The box contains a numbered ball. Once a ball is randomly removed from the box, its number is noted and it is returned to the box. Find the probability of the event that all elements of the sample are different. $1, 2, \dots, n$ nk

$$P(B) = \frac{n(B)}{n(U)} = \frac{A_n^k}{n^k}$$

3. There is a sphere numbered with numbers in the box. The spheres are carefully mixed and removed from the box one by one. Find the probability that the balls come out in the numbered sequence. $1, 2, \dots, n$ $1, 2, \dots, n$

$$P = \frac{1}{P_n} = \frac{1}{n!}$$

4. There is a ball of the same shape in the box. n Their number is red, the rest k and it is the sky. M balls are randomly drawn from the box ($m \leq n$). Find the probability that the ball is red among the selected m

$$balls \ l \ (l < m). \left(P = \frac{C_k^l \cdot C_{n-k}^{m-l}}{C_n^m} \right)$$

5. They threw a point inside the Egyptian triangle. Find the probability that the point is at a distance greater than 1 from the sides of the triangle.

Note that these types of problems are also called geometric probability problems, and the object thrown into a certain area is located in this area $D \ G \subset D$ the ratio of the size of the area (length, area, volume) to the size of the area is taken as the probability of the event falling into the area. The answer to this task: GD

$$P = \frac{6 - \frac{\pi}{2}}{6} = 1 - \frac{\pi}{12}$$

"Statistics and Probability" it is recommended to use the summative assessment criteria listed below.

1. Presents data according to statistical indicators that characterize the distribution, such as the numerical mean, median, mode, central tendency, and the largest difference; 2. Calculates the trend, dispersion, standard deviation according to the database given in various forms; 3. Constructs a normal distribution curve according to the selection (population) and presents it according to the situation; 4. Determines and presents data according to the conditions required in normal distribution with calculations; 5. Presents information

with a box-handle diagram; 6. Demonstrates understanding of concepts such as trial, event, space of elementary events, random event; 7. Applies the rule of adding probabilities to the calculation of probabilities of events; 8. Applies the rule of multiplying probabilities to calculating the probabilities of independent events; 9. Solves problems related to conditional probabilities [4; 459-460].

The result. 1) "Statistics and Probability" in the process of teaching the topics covered in the educational unit, the selection and application of task types should be focused on in order for students to become subjects of the verbs based on the expected results; 2) "Statistics and Probability" the inclusion of necessary terms in the content of students' active mathematical vocabulary in the process of teaching materials for the educational unit should be considered as an important didactic requirement; 3) "Statistics and Probability" it is advisable to take advantage of virtual tools (important links for teaching the course) and various worksheets as an additional resource in teaching the materials of the educational unit; 4) "Statistics and Probability" Since the materials of the educational unit belong to the "Geometry" content line, in the real pedagogical process dialectic unity (the system-structure' approach; whole-part relations) should be expected; 5) Expectation of the "opportunity-movement-quality" paradigm in the selection of tasks and their systematization has a positive effect on the efficiency of the educational process.

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